

Evaluation of the multi-actor partnership Flemish Green Deal 'Protein Shift on our plate'

Ines COTTIGNIE
Michiel DE BAUW
Erik MATHIJS

June 2025

Acknowledgements

This study was conducted within the FUTURES4FOOD project which was financially supported by BRAIN-be 2.0 research programme of Belspo (Belgian Science Policy Office). We want to acknowledge Caroline Amrom, Sien Luyten, Philippe Baret and Bart Van Looy for their involvement in the project. No conflicts of interests are declared by the authors. Neither the Belgian Science Policy Office nor any person acting on behalf of the Belgian Science Policy Office is responsible for the use which might be made of the following information. The authors are responsible for the content.

Credit author statement

Ines Cottignie: data collection, data analysis, writing – original draft,

Michiel De Bauw: writing – review & editing, supervision,

Erik Mathijs: conceptualisation, writing – review & editing, funding acquisition, supervision.

This document is shared under the Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International.

Cited as: Cottignie, I., De Bauw, M., Mathijs, E., 2025. Evaluation of the multi-actor partnership Flemish Green Deal 'Protein Shift on our plate', KU Leuven, DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.17054935

Abstract

This paper evaluates the Flemish Green Deal *Protein Shift on our Plate* (GDPS), a multi-actor partnership launched in 2021 to promote a dietary transition towards a 40/60 ratio of animal- to plant-based proteins and reduce overall protein intake by 2030. Using and adapting a transdisciplinary evaluation framework, we assessed the GDPS in terms of context, process, and intermediate outcomes. Data collection combined document analysis, semi-structured interviews (n=7), and an online questionnaire (n=28), representing 39% of the signatories. Results highlight strengths including a well-structured institutional setup, broad and diverse participation, constructive leadership, transparent communication, and valuable social learning. Intermediate outcomes included enhanced capacity building, strengthened networks, and improved systems, target, and transformation knowledge, with tangible impacts such as the co-created 'half-half' narrative. Challenges identified were limited resources, unequal commitment among signatories, risk of greenwashing, and difficulties in translating partnership outcomes into measurable consumer-level dietary change. Overall, the GDPS contributed to awareness raising, organisational change, and incremental steps in the protein transition, while underscoring the complexity of achieving systemic dietary shifts. Insights from this evaluation provide guidance for designing and strengthening future multi-actor sustainability partnerships.

Table of Contents

1.	Introduction	7
2	Methods	9
3	Results	13
3.1	<i>Context</i>	13
	3.1.1 Historical context	13
	3.1.2 Initiation	13
	3.1.3 Institutional context	14
3.2	<i>Process</i>	15
	3.2.1 Leadership	15
	3.2.2 Internal communication	16
	3.2.3 External communication	16
	3.2.4 Transparency	17
	3.2.5 Representation	17
	3.2.6 Conflict resolution	18
	3.2.7 Influence on the process	19
3.3	<i>Intermediate outcomes</i>	19
	3.3.1 Accountability	19
	3.3.2 Capacity building	20
	3.3.3 Knowledge	20
	3.3.4 Recognised impacts	22
	3.3.5 Social learning	24
4	Discussion & conclusion	24
5	References	27
6	Appendices	28
	<i>Appendix 1: Table with questions of the interviews and questionnaire, linked to the evaluation criteria</i>	29
	<i>Appendix 2: Ethics documents</i>	34
	<i>Appendix 3: Timeline including the most important GDPS milestones</i>	37
	<i>Appendix 4: Amount of signatories responding to the interview or questionnaire and in total involved in the GDPS, per stakeholder category</i>	38
	<i>Appendix 5: Principles endorsed by the GDPS signatories</i>	39
	<i>Appendix 6: Reasons for signatories to participate in the GDPS, related to capacity building and knowledge gaining</i>	39
	<i>Appendix 7: Various additional activities to advance the protein transition beyond the GDPS</i>	40

1. Introduction

Societal transitions are inherently wicked, characterised by uncertainty, complex interdependencies and difficulties to define consequences of actions (Rittel & Webber, 1973; Carley & Christie, 2000). Addressing wicked problems could benefit from the involvement of multiple actors who pool their resources in partnerships to solve problems which they cannot solve individually (Bryson et al., 2006; Frame, 2008). Various literature streams addressed multi-actor partnerships, taking a different perspective, for example from business, socio-ecological systems, transition, etc. Yet, despite their growing recognition as important mechanisms for enabling societal transitions, their strengths and pitfalls are understudied. In particular, there has been limited attention to the types of knowledge involved and the ways in which knowledge is (co)created within these partnerships.

The field of transdisciplinary science offers especially valuable insights, as it emphasises the co-creation of new knowledge required for societal transformation. This approach integrates interdisciplinary research with active collaboration among stakeholders. Ideal-typical transdisciplinary research projects have been designed, outlining distinct phases, activities, and guiding principles (Lang et al., 2012; Schneider et al., 2019). In this paper we applied and adapted an evaluation framework developed for transdisciplinary research projects to evaluate a multi-actor partnership in Flanders (the northern part of Belgium): the Green Deal ‘Protein Shift on our plate’.

Research question

We defined this research question: What can we learn from the strengths and pitfalls regarding the context, process and outcomes of this multi-actor partnership that can benefit this and future partnerships? Notably, its output was not part of the evaluation. In conclusion, the partnership itself served as the research object, rather than its methodological framework.

Case description

Inspired by the Dutch Green Deals and UN Sustainable Development Goals, the Department of Environment and Spatial Development of the Flemish Government launched their first Flemish Green Deals in 2017. They are innovative collaborative projects spanning three or four years, designed to facilitate the transition of sectors and organisations towards more sustainable practices. Through the exchange of knowledge and experiences, they serve as learning networks. Every type of organisation can apply to initiate a Green Deal. Once the initiation was approved by the Green Deal Council of the Government, additional organisations can voluntarily sign to participate in the specific Green Deal. This agreement with the Government includes the organisation’s commitment to make an effort for sustainable actions. Simultaneously, the Government addresses bottlenecks and highlights the commitments of the participating organisations, empowering them to create solutions collaboratively (Departement Omgeving, 2024d).

The specific case we were evaluating was the tenth Flemish Green Deal, named ‘Eiwitshift op ons bord’, translated as ‘Protein Shift on our plate’, henceforth abbreviated as GDPS. It was launched in April 2021 by the Department of Environment and Spatial Development itself and undersigned by its minister, and ran for four years. Inspired by the Dutch Green Protein Alliance, the GDPS objective was twofold: (1) to improve the ratio between animal and plant-based proteins in Flemish consumption towards a ratio of 40/60 animal/plant-based proteins by 2030, and (2) to reduce the total intake of proteins. The GDPS’s principal motivations for these objectives were the environmental footprint and health impacts

of the overconsumption of proteins and animal-based proteins specifically (Departement Omgeving, 2021).

By the time of the GDPS launch, 65 organisations signed the participation agreement, consequently becoming signatories, including food processing companies, caterers, supermarket chains, higher education and research institutes, cities, and nonprofits (Departement Omgeving, 2021). The actions signatories undertake were either raising awareness or changing the food environment (Departement Omgeving, 2021), which defined as “*The interface within the wider food system that mediates people’s food acquisition and consumption. It encompasses external dimensions such as the availability, prices, vendor and product properties, and promotional information; and personal dimensions such as the accessibility, affordability, convenience and desirability of food sources and products*” (Turner et al., 2018, p. 95). The most important GDPS milestones are documented in the timeline in Appendix 3.

In terms of governance, the GDPS steering committee included representatives from eight different signatories: three government agencies, two higher education institutes and three nonprofits. The chairperson, from the Department of Environment and Spatial Development of the Flemish Government, was responsible for the GDPS coordination and was the contact person for organisations to apply for and to withdraw from participation (Departement Omgeving, 2021).

In terms of positionality and involvement, the authors of this paper were also steering members. As the first author only started participating in the GDPS in November 2023, the present evaluation research provided a balanced view between insider understanding and external neutrality.

Table 1: Legend

GDPS	Flemish Green Deal ‘Eiwitshift op ons bord’, translated as ‘Protein Shift on Our Plate’
Signatory	Organisation that has signed the GDPS, consequently participating in the GDPS
Steering member	Representative of a signatory that was committed to steer the GDPS. This steering committee includes steering members from three governmental agencies, two higher education institutes and three nonprofit organisations
Chairperson	The steering member that was committed to coordinate the GDPS, representing the Department of Environment and Spatial Development of the Flemish Government
Respondents	A representative of a GDPS signatory who has completed the online questionnaire or participated in an interview, either from a regular signatory or from the steering committee
Colleague	Signatory employee that was not directly involved in the GDPS, unlike the signatory representative

2 Methods

A three-step methodology was used for our evaluation research.

Step 1: select evaluation framework

The evaluation process should commence with a precise definition of the objectives of the evaluation research (*bounding*), the evaluation *timing*, *focus* and *purpose* (Becker, 2004; Blackstock et al., 2007). In this paper, we were evaluating the context, process and outcomes of the GDPS (*bounding*). Since this evaluation was performed three years after the launch of the GDPS, one year before the finalisation, the timing was formative. Consequently, the insights gained by the evaluation still allowed for adaptations to the partnership. The evaluation *focus* was strategic, as the aim was to determine whether the process achieved the desired outcomes in alignment with the overarching objectives of transdisciplinary research. The evaluation *purpose* was improving and learning, in line with the transdisciplinary research purpose.

Based on literature review, it was decided to build the evaluation framework of this paper on the ones from Blackstock et al. (2007) and Hubeau et al. (2017). This was chosen since it is applicable to formative evaluations of participatory/transdisciplinary sustainability science¹ projects and extensively combines evaluation criteria regarding context, process and outcomes. To adapt the framework to our formative assessment, the outcomes are called intermediate outcomes.

Furthermore, two evaluation criteria were added: initiation as context criterium and knowledge as outcome criterium. Since the GDPS aims for a transition it was decided to evaluate the three types of knowledge needed for transition, according to Pohl & Hirsch Hadorn, 2007: (1) systems knowledge: knowledge about current problem or situation, “what is”; (2) target knowledge: knowledge about desired futures and values, “what should be”; (3) transformation knowledge: knowledge about the necessary steps to move from the current to the desired future, how to get from ‘what is’ to ‘what should be’. Table 2 represents the final evaluation framework with its criteria and descriptions and Figure 1 comprises the evaluation method structure used in this paper.

Step 2: data collection

To ensure quality, we have given thorough consideration to the selection and collection of both data and samples, including data triangulation. The official documents written by the steering committee throughout the three years of the GDPS were collected for document analysis: the initiation report (Departement Omgeving, 2021), the official website (Departement Omgeving, 2024b), the food routine report (Departement Omgeving, 2023a) and the yearly progress reports (Departement Omgeving, 2022, 2023b, 2024c).

Based on literature study and these official GDPS documents, questions were drawn up to collect experiences and perspectives of signatories about the context, process and intermediate outcome evaluation criteria. These questions (see Appendix 1) were open ended for semi-structured 60-90 minutes face-to-face interviews (24/05/2024-08/07/2024) and both closed and open ended for the online LimeSurvey questionnaire (19/06/2024-11/08/2024). Combining these two data collection methods was chosen to collect data in an efficient way from a range of signatories across locations without losing context-specific information. Potential interviewees were contacted via personal mail

¹ Blackstock defines participatory sustainability science as the “co-generation of knowledge about socio-ecological systems drawing on multiple understandings in an ongoing collective dialogue in order to transform practice, where academics and stakeholders are all co-researchers” (Blackstock et al., 2007).

messages after a purposeful selection to obtain a diverse array of views. All seven contacted signatory representatives agreed to participate in the interview. We announced the questionnaire in the GDPS plenary session of May 2024, and the chairperson contacted all signatory representatives with the request to complete the questionnaire. 28 complete and valid questionnaire responses were acquired, resulting in a response rate of 38%.

All respondents were representatives of a GDPS signatory, both regular and steering members, either completing the online questionnaire or participating in an interview. The 35 respondents were from 33 unique signatories, representing 39%. A purposeful sample was obtained, seeking maximum diversity and representativeness in level of engagement of the signatory, the year that they joined the GDPS, the respondent's age and role (Table 3), and stakeholder category (Appendix 4). All categories with more than two signatories were represented. We are confident in the robustness of the data despite the sample size. Table 2 documents the overview of the data collection methods used for the respective evaluation criteria.

Step 3: data analysis

The interviews were transcribed using Transkriptor, followed by a manual researcher review. The data from the official documents, interviews and questionnaire was pre-coded and coded through the MAXQDA (24.4.1 with integrated AI Assist Premium) software. For the three respondents involved since 2024, only a selection of their data was used due to a potential bias in their assessment capacity: exclusively their organisational activities, examples of activities of other stakeholders contributing to the protein transition, internal and external reactions about their participation, effort obligation opinion and reasons to participate. For the two cases with dual responses from the same signatory, only the closed-ended data from the representative with the longest involvement was included. However, the open-ended responses from the junior representatives were retained to incorporate additional perspectives.

Subsequently, all statements were connected within the context into a coherent whole. The in-depth analysed data was linked with the evaluation criteria and was grouped in strengths and pitfalls, indicated with (+) and (-) respectively. One should note that some results could be categorised in multiple evaluation criteria.

The research approach was reviewed and approved by the ethical commission of UCLouvain and was recognised by the ethical commission of KU Leuven (number G-2021-4619). All data was handled confidential and anonymous (Appendix 2).

Figure 1: Assessment method

Table 2: List of evaluation criteria, their description and data collection methods

(based on Blackstock et al., 2007; Hubeau et al., 2017)

Evaluation criteria	Description	Data collection methods		
		Documents	Interviews	Questionnaire
Context				
Historical context	The attitudes, perceptions and relationships that exist at the start of the process based on previous events and activities	X	X	
Initiation (new)	The activities that have been carried out to initiate the project	X	X	X
Institutional context	The structure in which participants collaborate in accordance to their role and formal and informal rules of the game	X	X	X
Process				
Leadership	Leadership explicates the role of stakeholders	X	X	X
Internal communication	Frequency and quality of flow of information within the partnership	X	X	X
External communication	Frequency and quality of flow of information about the partnership towards the outside world	X		
Transparency	Actors understand the reasoning behind decision making	X	X	X
Representation	The diversity of views of actors	X	X	X
Conflict resolution	Solution of conflict between participants and number of conflicts that occurred due to diversity of views	X	X	X
Influence on the process	How the stakeholders influence the output and outcomes of the process	X	X	X
Intermediate outcomes				
Accountability	Whether the participant's core constituencies are satisfied; also the perceived legitimacy of the process	X	X	X
Capacity building	Improvement of skills and relationships for participating in future processes	X	X	X
Knowledge (new)	Systems, target and transformation knowledge generated	X	X	X
Recognised impacts	Changes in stakeholder perceptions attributed to the process	X	X	X
Social learning	Change in individual values and behaviour due to collaboration, in turn influencing collective culture and norms – focusing mainly on regime-niche interactions		X	X

Table 3: Descriptive statistics of responses from interviews and questionnaire

Topic	Category	Amount per category, n=35
Age of respondent	27-39 year	16
	40-52 year	13
	53-65 year	5
	Unknown	1
Role of respondent	Steering member	9
	Both coordinator and executor of predefined actions of their organisation	13
	Solely coordinator of predefined actions of their organisation	9
	Solely executor of predefined actions of their organisation	4
Year that signatory joined GDPS	2021	28
	2022	3
	2023	2
	2024	2
Presence of signatory at group activities (indicator of level of engagement)	Never	1 (joined in 2024)
	Rarely	2
	Sometimes	6
	Often	19
	Always	6
	Unknown	1

3 Results

We described the results qualitatively according to the evaluation criteria (Table 2). If no source reference was mentioned, the information was obtained by the interview and questionnaire data.

3.1 Context

3.1.1 Historical context

On the level of food system stakeholders, the chairperson identified certain organisations as potential signatories (like a supermarket chain and nonprofit organisations) as a result of previous successful projects and consequently mutual trust (+). On the level of Flemish consumers, there was a slight increase in openness to plant-based food and environmental awareness observed according to the former chairman of the GDPS (+). On political level, the topic of the protein transition was first broached within the Flemish Government in 2018. With the inauguration of the Jambon Government in 2019, Flemish food policy was prioritised. In 2020, also the Farm to Fork Strategy was initiated in the European Union. In February 2021, the Flemish Protein Strategy was launched, with sustainable protein consumption as one of the strategical themes. After this long run-up (-), these developments provided the impetus for the GDPS to gain political momentum (+) (Departement Omgeving, 2021).

3.1.2 Initiation

In February 2020, the Green Deal Council endorsed the GDPS concept, and after further refinements, the initiative received political approval in October 2020 and was launched in April 2021. It was acknowledged that the GDPS can contribute to the Flemish Protein Strategy as a concrete action (Departement Omgeving, 2021). The GDPS initiation process involved multiple exchanges including workshops and individual outreach efforts by the former chairperson with interested partners, engaging a diverse array of signatories (+). The chairperson continuously refined the objectives, scope, and structure based on feedback from the expanding network of partners to reach a final proposition (+). The latter was launched during information sessions to garner interested partners.

To gauge pressure on the regime, signatories were asked to recall reactions regarding their participation to the GDPS from both other organisations and within their own organisation. Some respondents could not recall any reactions to their own participation. Respondents reported that reactions from other organisations regarding their participation in the GDPS were generally positive (+), with a few exceptions (-). Participation appeared to have been well received by other organisations already involved in the topic, feeling empowerment in their own efforts by the GDPS. It was for example endorsed that there was ministerial support for the GDPS. Some signatories also noted that their partners were enthusiastic that the signatory puts its shoulder to the wheel. One respondent observes that their partners and customers were unaware of the existence of Flemish Green Deals and reports some confusion between Flemish and European Green Deals. A few respondents received negative feedback, particularly from partners in the meat industry who perceive the initiative as portraying their products unfavourably and regard the GDPS as overly extreme or restrictive. As preparations and the launch of the GDPS occurred online during the Covid-19 pandemic, media attention was limited, potentially resulting in fewer external reactions for signatories starting in 2021.

From within their organisation, most respondents received positive or neutral feedback regarding their GDPS participation (+), with the importance and relevance of the initiative being widely acknowledged. Some viewed participation in the GDPS as a positive reinforcement of their existing sustainability efforts and some regard their involvement self-evident. However, others reported ongoing controversy and resistance within their organisation (-). Some colleagues within their organisation remained sceptical or

reluctant to fully embrace the transition, expressing for example concerns about providing predominantly plant-based catering for events. Some respondents experienced no or minimal feedback or recognition of their involvement by their colleagues. The degree of awareness, engagement and support differs across signatories. It appeared to differ depending on the culture, priorities, size and communication dynamics of the organisation. There was sometimes the perception that few individuals were aware of their organisation's involvement in the GDPS.

3.1.3 Institutional context

As one can conclude from the case description in the introduction, the GDPS had a well-structured institutional context (+). The GDPS signatories also had to endorse predefined principles drawn up by the Flemish Government, creating a clear common ground (+), see Appendix 5 (Departement Omgeving, 2021).

The budget allocated to the GDPS was rather limited in comparison to its elaborate twofold objective and part of the budget was also retrieved ad-hoc (-). The Flemish Government provided budget for the employment of about 1.5 FTE, including their chairman, and for a modest working budget, among others used for providing catering and facilitation at the GDPS gatherings. Signatories were not paid to participate in the GDPS, although some received budget from the Flemish Government for specific research studies or projects contributing to the twofold objective, like monitoring protein consumption and developing the 'halfhalf' narrative.

Important to note about the institutional context was that all Flemish Green Deals are structured as an effort obligation rather than a commitment to specific predefined outcomes. It was stated that signatories commit to do what was within their capabilities (Departement Omgeving, 2024d). Organisations wishing to participate propose their own actions, which were then assessed by the steering committee based on their ambition and relevance.

The large majority of respondents indicated that their organisation agreed that this effort obligation was positive (+). It was well-received by signatories as it lowers the barriers to participation, allowing for the involvement of organisations that might not have otherwise engaged, even if their initial contributions were relatively modest. Respondents noted that this approach facilitates greater risk-taking and experimentation by the signatories, with inspiration proving more effective than compulsion. Some respondents also noted that they would have been unable to commit to an outcome-based obligation due to their reliance on external factors.

However, some respondents argued that signatories should have the option of entering into a results-based agreement, to encourage more robust engagement and taking significant action with clearly defined and binding subobjectives. Some respondents were concerned about the potential for greenwashing (-), where signatories may claim participation without enacting meaningful changes. The steering committee was cognisant of this risk and, to mitigate it, transparently publishes the actions undertaken by the signatories. In addition, in 2022 less active signatories were personally contacted by the chairperson, resulting in slightly higher involvement. Nevertheless, the committee recognised that it cannot fully verify the authenticity and sincerity of all actions and signatories due to limited resources. Green Deals were never initiated to do so.

3.2 Process

3.2.1 Leadership

The various roles and responsibilities of the signatories, steering members and the chairperson of the GDPS were outlined in the official documents which are publicly available and were offered to all signatories (+).

There were no explicit wordings that assign responsibility for the outcomes to the chairperson. In practice, the chairperson was the driver of the GDPS: facilitating and organising meetings. The food routines working groups were either lead by the chairperson or other signatories who pursue specific actions informed by their expertise and positions. In other Flemish Green Deals the Government consistently serve as the point of contact, content expert and signatory, but almost never as the driver. The former chairperson had expressed ease with taking these multiple roles, including that of driver.

The steering committee was responsible for monitoring and guarding the implementation of the GDPS, assessing the entry and exit of organisations, the yearly reporting towards the Green Deal Council and delivering the final report (Departement Omgeving, 2021). They made decisions in consultation with each other via mail or via steering committee meetings. According to the steering members themselves, the distribution of responsibilities within their committee was not always easy (-). There was the perception that the Flemish Government had taken on excessive responsibility in an effort to be inclusive and retain signatories, which had resulted in an imbalance of commitment, being an ongoing challenge. One of the steering members perceived the overall mandate and operational approach (modus operandi) of the GDPS as unclear, with characteristics of both a transitional arena and a free-flowing community of interest.

Nearly all responding signatories concurred that the roles within the GDPS were clearly defined (+). However, three (10%) did not agree. One of them was not aware of the existence of a steering committee and how signatories could participate in decision-making. Another respondent expressed uncertainty about the composition of the steering committee and the scope of its decision-making authority. This indicates that these two latter respondents did not read the offered official documents and had a low involvement, despite their participation from the launch in 2021. All respondents who agreed that the roles were clear also expressed satisfaction with the current allocation of roles (+). One respondent suggested issuing a call for interested signatories to join the steering committee, from which a select few could be chosen to complement the existing members. Unaware about this specific suggestion, one steering member noted that a small steering committee was necessary to avoid "diffuse responsibility" and to strengthen the connection between policy and research. However, this steering member also self-critically stated that the steering members were already strongly committed to the protein transition, being not that diverse in opinions.

One steering member specifically showed their appreciation for the organic, project-based approach underpinned by a general framework, rather than a highly structured, hierarchical model. The steering committee had endeavoured to strike a balance by avoiding a top-down approach while ensuring that signatories' ideas and initiatives were given a platform to be developed (+). Next to that, the steering committee had expressed a desire for individuals from signatories to take the role of driver within the various working groups. While there was enthusiasm of signatories for contributing through brainstorming, providing feedback, and supporting research and communication, there were several barriers to make more substantial commitments for the GDPS in general (see Intermediate outcomes < Accountability). It was noted that there was a need to carefully manage expectations and align them with the capacities of the signatories (-).

Throughout the three years of the GDPS, several switches of representatives of signatories and steering committee took place. The chairperson also changed, although the former chairperson remained continuously involved in the steering committee. These switches probably had no negative impact on the process, since they were not brought up by the respondents.

The responses suggested that the power dynamics were regarded as appropriate, with no major concerns raised regarding undue influences (+). Respondents did not perceive any power imbalances within the GDPS. Several respondents highlighted the flat, collaborative structure, noting the absence of dominant stakeholders or top-down control. Still, some respondents noted that they lack sufficient insight into the decision-making dynamics of the steering committee to fully assess the balance of power.

3.2.2 Internal communication

In the GDPS there was multidirectional communication between regular signatories and steering members via email, webinars, online and in-person workshops, company visits, food routine working groups and plenary meetings. The latter were held two times online due to Covid-19 restrictions and five times in-person (see milestones Appendix 3). Signatories also contributed to annual progress reports using a template provided by the steering committee. These reports were highlighted by respondents as a key touchpoint for information exchange with the steering committee and with fellow signatories.

Respondents generally felt that the information flow from the steering committee was sufficient (+). Furthermore, three (10%) respondents expressed a preference for more concise email communications, noting that there was sometimes an oversupply of information. The accessibility and responsiveness of the chairperson were also noted as positive aspects.

Both steering committee and signatory respondents indicated that the current level of information exchange coming from other signatories was adequate (+), considering existing time constraints. However, it was noted that some either fail to submit their input or miss the deadline for their input for the annual progress reports (-). As a novel suggestion through the questionnaire, some steering members expressed a desire for more information exchange about the processes of signatories (-), including the challenges encountered, to facilitate learnings from these experiences.

According to almost all respondents, the information exchange within the GDPS was regarded as suitable to achieving its objectives (+). While respondents perceived the research findings and new product developments presented to be both interesting and useful, others felt that this information did not always directly lead to concrete actions or behavioural changes by companies and consumers.

3.2.3 External communication

Diverse communication about the GDPS occurred towards other organisations and consumers (+). Initially external communication consisted of the GDPS website that was publicly available from 2021 on the web domain of the Department of Environment and Spatial Development (010 - Eiwitshift op ons bord | Departement Omgeving, 2024). Because the signatories shared their wish to obtain a common narrative to advise consumers, they had designed the complexity-informed, evidence-based 'halfhalf' narrative during an intense co-creation process. The narrative was subsequently incorporated in the general information on food guidelines and in specific instruments and materials. The 'halfhalf' website was available since 2023 on the web domain of the nonprofit 'Vlaams Instituut Gezond Leven' (Halfhalf | Gezond Leven, 2024). This institute also linked ecological sustainability with the nutritional triangle since 2021 (Departement Omgeving, 2021). The 'halfhalf' website launch was combined with a

communication campaign in November 2023 towards consumers via social media using videos and e-guides and via physically nudging material in among other supermarkets and canteens. The social media channel LinkedIn, the newsletter and the website of the Flemish Green Deals was also used for specific GDPS outreach (Departement Omgeving, 2024c).

3.2.4 Transparency

Almost all signatories comprehended the rationale behind the decisions made within the GDPS (+). However, some respondents had found it difficult to articulate specific decisions beyond the 'half-half' campaign. Two other respondents indicated that they personally understand these decisions, whereas others within their organisation did not necessarily share this understanding. The responses suggest that there was generally adequate transparency concerning the decisions made by the GDPS steering committee (+). Respondents felt that the committee effectively communicates both the information and the rationale behind its decisions to the signatories. While the steering committee was willing to address questions and provide explanations, some respondents propose either more proactive communication regarding future plans and priorities, or perceived that the decision-making process could be more transparent including their role, composition and meeting reports. Since all Flemish Green Deals are organised as effort obligations, the GDPS steering committee did not explicitly communicate about the reasoning behind this strategy and how they mitigate the risk for greenwashing. Yet, this topic was not mentioned as a concern by the respondents about the statement about transparency.

3.2.5 Representation

There were 84 signatories in the GDPS at the time of the launch of the questionnaire (Appendix 4), including mostly niche but also regime players (+). The signatory representatives were junior profiles to CEO's, sustainability employees to marketing and communication experts.

There was consensus among respondents that the GDPS was open to any actor who can contribute to shifting protein consumption (+), confirming the official GDPS documentation (see Appendix 5, nr 9). While there was a screening process in which new signatories' commitments were reviewed and approved by the steering committee, the overarching approach was to maintain a low threshold for participation. Some respondents noted that also organisations that might be perceived as having opposing interests were welcomed, provided they genuinely support the twofold objective of the GDPS. The GDPS aimed to bring together a diverse array of stakeholders from across the food system, recognising that everyone has a role to play in supporting this transition.

Most respondents agreed that the various organisations necessary to achieve the objectives were already involved in the GDPS (+). Several respondents suggested that certain important stakeholders were either missing or underrepresented. The suggested stakeholders were the agricultural sector, the meat industry, the hospitality sector (HoReCa), primary and secondary schools, youth associations, healthcare institutions, media companies, large corporations outside the food sector and consumer organisations. At the same time, respondents raised concerns regarding how to meaningfully engage these potentially new stakeholder categories whose interests may conflict with the GDPS objectives and/or for whom the timing may not yet be appropriate.

It was important to note that some of these suggested stakeholders were already indirectly addressed by the GDPS. For instance, the agricultural sector was involved in the Flemish Protein Strategy and was represented and influenced by 'VLAM', 'ILVO', 'Arvesta' and the Agency Agriculture and Fisheries, which were signatories of the GDPS. The hospitality sector (HoReCa) and schools were indirectly targeted through, e.g., signatory caterers, or through nonprofit signatories that run projects involving these stakeholders. The hospitality sector was also represented since 2024 through the participation of

'Horeca Vlaanderen'. The Flemish Green Deal 'Duurzame Zorg' (Sustainable Care) initiated in 2023 also included sustainable food in healthcare institutions. Moreover, the GDPS chairperson was also involved in that Green Deal to actively exchange insights (Departement Omgeving, 2024a). In addition, consumers were targeted by the 'halfhalf' campaign and other awareness-raising actions or challenges organised by signatories.

Almost all respondents reported experiencing a safe and open environment within the GDPS (+). They felt confident in sharing their opinions and engaging in discussions, even when differing views were present. The collaborative nature of the initiative, coupled with a strong sense of community, fostered an atmosphere in which individuals felt comfortable exchanging ideas and working together towards the shared objectives. However, one supermarket chain respondent experienced the environment as "not always easy", since there was no real partnership at this moment with the competing supermarket chains.

3.2.6 Conflict resolution

No respondents indicated that disagreements occurred often or very often, and none expressed dissatisfaction with how the disagreements were managed (+). Certain respondents even did not observe any disagreement. Occasional disagreements among GDPS signatories were reported, though these were not per se perceived as conflicts. All reported disagreements were shared below:

-Two respondents highlighted disagreements concerning the role of meat, noting a perception of divergent viewpoints and a lack of openness to alternative perspectives by signatories advocating for a 100% plant-based diet. Additionally, one respondent associated with agriculture reports receiving a range of critical questions from other signatories regarding their GDPS contribution.

-Some examples of disagreements centred around the role of ultra-processed plant-based products in the protein transition. Some signatories advocated for the promotion of these products, while others remained sceptical about these products. Nevertheless, they generally managed to reach compromises, emphasising the importance of inclusivity and avoiding alienation of consumers.

-The process of designing the 'halfhalf' narrative was generally regarded as a positive experience despite some disagreements or concerns, with a consensus being achieved among signatories with varying interests.

Within the working groups, differences in pace were also evident, with some signatories seeking rapid action while others favoured more extensive discussion and relationship-building (Departement Omgeving, 2023a). Facilitators endeavoured to be adaptable in addressing the needs of each working group.

-The steering committee requested the signatories to also spread the 'halfhalf' narrative through their organisations during or after the period of the campaign. Some respondents expressed concerns about the limited span of the official 'halfhalf' campaign by 'Vlaams Instituut Gezond Leven' to consumers, resulting in hesitation by the management of their organisations to effectively implement 'halfhalf' in their own communication strategy.

Overall, signatories expressed satisfaction with the management of these differences, maintaining a focus on the shared objectives (+).

One signatory was withdrawn from the initiative by the former GDPS chairperson due to their repeated failure to respond, provide input, or attend meetings, despite multiple attempts to engage them. The reasons for this lack of engagement remain unknown. Additionally, two signatories voluntarily withdrew

their participation due to personal health issues or family commitments. The steering committee respondents did not perceive these three discontinuations as conflicts. They were communicated in the annual report, without shaming them and without stating the reason for discontinuation. Although regrettable, a steering member stated that these discontinuations were considered necessary and positive steps to preserve the integrity of the GDPS. All other 62 signatories active and 22 additional signatories joined after the initiation of the GDPS without launching specific calls for organisations (+), gradually over the three years (Departement Omgeving, 2022, 2023b, 2024c).

3.2.7 Influence on the process

According to the official GDPS documentation, each signatory had the right to request modifications to the GDPS (Departement Omgeving, 2021). None of the respondents indicated that they 'disagree or 'totally disagree' the statement that sharing their viewpoints or knowledge has had an influence on the GDPS (+). While some respondents indicated that they did not share their viewpoints or knowledge, there was a greater sharing of knowledge compared to sharing viewpoints. When signatories did express their viewpoints, they felt that these were valued and taken into consideration (+). However, the extent to which individual contributions directly impacted the outcome remains uncertain. Overall, there was a prevailing sense that knowledge sharing within the GDPS facilitated mutual learning and influenced the process, even if the direct impact is not always easily quantifiable. For example, advice from signatories regarding specific terminology was subsequently incorporated into the 'halfhalf' narrative. Additionally, during plenary meetings and webinars, signatories were offered the opportunity to present their perspectives and share their expertise.

3.3 Intermediate outcomes

3.3.1 Accountability

Most signatories agreed on feeling jointly responsible for the outcomes of the GDPS (+). Some respondents reported a limited sense of responsibility for the GDPS outcomes, attributing this to the perception that the objectives were vague and that the outcomes were challenging to measure, which complicates the ability to take ownership over the outcomes. While the initiative produced some tangible outcomes such as an increase in plant-based offerings, some signatories acknowledge that the direct connection to the GDPS was not always evident. Two respondents also stated that they were helping to obtain the objectives with their own actions, but did not feel responsible for the GDPS outcomes as a whole. Another respondent also remarked a sense of responsibility of most people involved in the GDPS, but recognised that not its entire organisation exhibits the same level of responsibility.

The level of commitment among signatories towards accelerating the protein transition was mixed (-). Time and resources were frequently cited as barriers. One respondent suggested that more concrete tips for external funding opportunities could be shared within the GDPS. Another potential limiting factor for more substantial commitments might be the lack of a clear added value (business case) of the GDPS for certain signatories, a hypothesis that warrants further investigation. Some corporate signatories also stated that if the GDPS could be organised on Belgian level, more substantial commitments could be made by their organisation. Other signatories suggested that establishing more concrete short-term objectives could be advantageous, as it might lead to a greater sense of actionability and ownership, provided opportunities to celebrate incremental achievements, and fostered further collaboration. It was suggested that working groups could be established for each specific short-term objective, incorporating key individuals who possess the authority to implement changes within their respective organisations.

Yet almost all respondents considered the outcomes of the GDPS to be valued by their organisation (+), although the extent of this perceived value varies. Some viewed the outcomes as beneficial for raising awareness and highlighting the issue, while others reported difficulties in achieving complete organisational buy-in. One respondent noted that “the 40/60 ratio is neither accurate nor feasible”.

3.3.2 Capacity building

Almost all respondents indicated that their involvement in the GDPS had improved their skills (such as communication and empathy skills) for engaging in future collaborations (+). Specific learnings mentioned include broadening in perspectives, navigating complex transition projects and collective problem-solving. Additionally, some respondents highlighted more general advancements in skills related to product development and marketing.

Almost all indicated that the GDPS results in the establishment or strengthening of professional connections that may foster future collaborations (+), aligning with the claimed benefits of Green Deals (Departement Omgeving, 2024d). There were increased interactions with other signatories, several tangible collaborations have already been realised, and some connections were anticipated to extend beyond the duration of the GDPS. Some respondents also expressed their appreciation that the GDPS provides them opportunities to remain engaged with the market and to learn from the experiences of others. One academic respondent stated that: “making connections is also part of our duties, providing that service”.

Participation in the GDPS had also enabled almost all respondents to gain a better understanding of the complexity associated with the protein transition (+). Indicated examples were that they have acquired insights into the various stakeholders, initiatives, and factors involved, recognising that the process was neither simple nor straightforward. Some specified that transition demands the coordination of numerous small actions and changes throughout the food system, rather than relying on a singular, overarching solution. Some signatories also exemplified that they developed an awareness of the challenges inherent in driving behavioural change, noting that consumers frequently find it difficult to perceive the environmental impact of their individual choices and were often resistant to substantial dietary changes. Different respondents mentioned that the ‘half-half’ narrative development was especially insightful regarding deeper understanding of how people think and how to communicate effectively about the protein transition.

One can conclude that there was at least some beneficial capacity building on these three themes resulting from their GDPS involvement. Interesting to mention was that capacity building was not perceived as a major reason to participate for signatories, more detailed results about this in Appendix 6.

3.3.3 Knowledge

The signatories self-reported that on average their participation had led to most insights about target knowledge, subsequently about transformation knowledge and least about systems knowledge. Gaining transformation knowledge was the most important reason for respondents to participate in the GDPS, compared to the other predefined reasons (Appendix 6 describes detailed results). There were instances where withholding knowledge from other signatories provides a competitive advantage, like between competing supermarket chains and food processors (-). This could pose a significant barrier to the protein transition.

Systems Knowledge

According to the official reports (Departement Omgeving, 2022, 2023a), knowledge and insights were shared about the food routines, defined as ‘protein culture’, ‘food skills’ and ‘healthy, high-quality and safe supply’. Moreover, a systems mapping workshop was organised for those willing and able to be involved. Some respondents felt they possessed sufficient knowledge about the issues related to current Flemish consumption of animal proteins prior to engaging in the project. All other respondents reported an increase in this type of knowledge (+) due to their participation, ranging from a modest expansion to extensive.

Most respondents also gained knowledge about the issues related with the Flemish protein overconsumption (+). Some of them stated that they were previously unaware of these issues. However, the GDPS did not specifically address the problems associated with overconsumption, resulting in some respondents indicating that they did not gain any knowledge on this aspect. The primary focus of the GDPS was on facilitating the transition from animal-based to more plant-based protein consumption, rather than directly tackling the issue of overconsumption. In conclusion, the GDPS offered a general awareness of the issues but did not explore in depth the specific challenges and drivers related to protein overconsumption in Flanders.

Most respondents indicated that they have gained knowledge on the issues related to the Flemish food environment by the GDPS (+). Some respondents self-reported that they already possessed a thorough understanding of it, given that it falls within their area of expertise. One respondent indicated the wish to know more about food policy and its possibilities to influence this.

Target knowledge

Respondents acquired valuable knowledge into the envisioned future of the Flemish protein transition, resulting from their participation in the GDPS (+). The envisioned future was already pointed out at the launch of the GDPS with the twofold objective (Departement Omgeving, 2021).

However, it was not decided yet what the specific role of ultra-processed plant-based products was in the envisioned future and consequently how to communicate about these products (-). There were workshops organised on this topic within the GDPS. It was decided to pause these since most had the feeling they first needed more scientific clarity about the health aspects of this product category, before developing a shared vision.

The extent of knowledge respondents gained regarding the values and norms of Flemish stakeholders concerning the protein transition varied. Most respondents gained sufficient knowledge or more (+). Some specifically indicated that they became familiar with the diverse perspectives and shared viewpoints of the various stakeholders involved.

Transformation knowledge

Almost all respondents have acquired at least some knowledge about the necessary steps required to achieve a protein transition in Flanders (+). The extent to which they had gained transformation knowledge was mixed (-). The complexity of the challenge was acknowledged, highlighting the necessity for multiple incremental positive actions rather than a singular all-encompassing solution. Research and innovation was also discussed (Departement Omgeving, 2023a).

3.3.4 Recognised impacts

Respondents were asked about the impacts resulting from their participation in the GDPS on their respective signatory organisation. In addition, the impact of the GDPS on Flemish consumers were examined. Important remark: isolating the impact of the GDPS was impossible, as other initiatives and broader societal trends also influence organisations and consumers. Few respondents indicated that the evolving societal attitudes towards climate and sustainability seem to have more significant effect on for example mitigating resistance towards the protein transition and increasing environmental consciousness than their specific involvement in the GDPS.

Recognised impacts on organisational level

Although respondents personally recognised the impacts of the GDPS, a common remark was that greater effort was required on their part to communicate effectively within their organisation. Many respondents felt there were "small pawns" within their organisation and note a lack of communication about their participation to other levels (-). The extent of this communication appeared to be influenced by factors such as the organisation's size and the specific role of the GDPS within the organisation's overall strategy.

Most respondents indicated that the GDPS enlarges awareness within their respective organisations regarding the environmental impact of food (+). The involvement of signatories in the GDPS had varied effects on the awareness. It was further noted that certain colleagues of their organisation neither concur with nor endorse the protein transition. Seven respondents (23%) felt that the initiative had not significantly enhanced awareness within their organisation. Conversely, five other respondents (17%) already possessed a strong awareness.

The involvement of signatories in the GDPS facilitated conversations about the protein transition within their respective organisations (+), though to varying extents. Two respondents indicated that the topic was already fully discussable. Respondents indicated that the GDPS offers a framework and a common language for addressing the protein transition. Some respondents exemplified that the GDPS aids in developing and communicating their own strategies more effectively.

It appeared to be challenging for a lot of respondents to assess whether involvement in the GDPS contributes to reducing resistance towards the protein transition and to increasing motivation to accelerate the shift within their organisation. Most agreed that the GDPS attributes to reducing resistance and to more motivation to accelerate the shift within their organisation (+). In certain instances, the GDPS provided a framework or a "hook" that facilitates the acceptance of protein transition initiatives and provides allies. Conversely, in other signatories, the GDPS had limited direct impact, with the protein transition being viewed primarily as an element of the organisation's broader sustainability strategy. It was also exemplified that the involvement of competitors further stimulate motivation, as they were driven to keep up with the others. Another statement of a respondent was that colleagues who prioritise financial considerations over environmental or health benefits experience more resistance towards the protein transition.

Some respondents expressed the feeling that the GDPS merely enumerates activities that were already planned before the GDPS by the signatories, leading to the perception that it primarily served as formalising and emphasising pre-existing plans, rather than to catalyse significant new initiatives. However, the signatory responses appeared to contradict this criticism, as the vast majority indicated that their involvement led to the implementation of various actions that would not have occurred otherwise (+). Still, for some respondents it was difficult to self-report if the involvement in the GDPS resulted in new actions, as the signatory already had a well-defined food strategy and existing plans to

address the protein transition. Three respondents indicated that the GDPS had not led to any additional activities (-), being two nonprofit signatories actively engaged in the protein transition and one retailer. As examples of implementation of actions that would not have occurred without the GDPS, several respondents cited the development of the 'halfhalf' narrative and subsequently spreading it as a notable example. Other mentioned initiatives included organising additional webinars, writing articles, participating in thematic challenges about the protein transition and increasing plant-based catering.

It was interesting to note that most respondents classified all their protein transition-promoting activities as part of the GDPS actions. Further, numerous signatories engaged in various additional activities to advance the protein transition beyond the GDPS (+). Respondents also noted that there were activities outside the GDPS which may contribute to the protein transition (Appendix 7), potentially influenced by the GDPS (+).

Recognised impacts on consumer level

Some respondents suggested that expectations on changes on consumer level by the GDPS should be tempered, given the likelihood that some initiatives would have also occurred without the GDPS and given the limited budget allocated to the GDPS. The 'halfhalf' communication campaign targeting Flemish consumers for example was partially overruled by campaigns with larger budgets promoting among others local meat and dairy products.

It was not yet thoroughly investigated whether there had been a significant reduction in total protein intake among Flemish consumers. Almost all respondents disagreed that the GDPS resulted in a total protein intake reduction in Flanders, or were unsure about it (-). One respondent also noted that reducing and monitoring protein consumption presents a challenging objective, which has not been actively addressed within the GDPS. Some respondents observed an increased emphasis on high-protein products in supermarkets for muscle building, which could potentially lead to an increase in overall protein intake rather than a decrease.

Respondents hold diverse views regarding the extent to which the GDPS influences Flemish perceptions about plant-based eating as "normal". The majority of respondents indicated that the statement was difficult to assess. Four respondents (13%) disagreed with the statement; one of them emphasises persistent resistance, noting that many individuals in their environment continue to be committed meat eaters. A bit more than one third agreed that the GDPS contributes to this perception shift (-). Some examples showed that they were optimistic that acceptance and normalisation of plant-based eating was increasing, even if actual willingness to alter dietary habits has not yet fully materialised.

The Belgian Food Consumption Survey of 2014 reported that the Flemish diet consisted of 38.6% plant-based proteins and 61.4% animal-based proteins (De Ridder et al., 2016). The subsequent Belgian Food Consumption Survey of 2022-2023 reveals a slight increase in plant-based protein intake to 41.3%, with a corresponding decrease in animal-based protein intake to 58.7% in Flanders (Rubens et al., 2024) with different consumption patterns across provinces. These numbers suggested that the GDPS potentially could have contributed to altering the ratio of plant-based to animal-based protein consumption in Flanders (+/-). When these results were presented in a GDPS plenary session, some signatories experienced this as a reality check. Nevertheless, respondents observed indications of increasing openness to the thematic, higher sales of plant-based alternatives and a greater number of plant-based options at events. Respondents also considered the GDPS as a positive development with the potential to accelerate the transition towards more sustainable diets in the long term.

3.3.5 Social learning

There was a consensus among respondents that participation in the GDPS delivers them with valuable knowledge and insights derived from the experiences of other stakeholders within the food system (+). Some exemplified that they have acquired information on innovative food products as well as the challenges and complexities associated with transforming the food system. These exchanges had significantly broadened their understanding of the diverse perspectives present within the food sector.

4 Discussion & conclusion

According to the **context** results, the GDPS was launched at an advantageous moment in a constructive and well-structured way (Blackstock et al., 2007) with a societally relevant topic. The participation of a diverse range of signatories demonstrated broad support for the twofold objective. Despite the greenwashing challenge, the effort-based model was regarded as the most appropriate for driving this complex transition, even though it may not yield the most immediate and tangible outcomes.

The **process** results showed favourable conditions for a fruitful process (Blackstock et al., 2007), including clear and desired roles, sufficient and relevant information flow, safe and open environment where viewpoints and knowledge were mostly shared, healthy conflict resolution and diverse representation. The diversity of the signatories and its representatives was both valuable and challenging. Junior profiles for example did not always have the mandate to influence their organisation. Getting a purposeful selection of signatory representatives and new signatories from different stakeholder categories at the table for specific challenges could be beneficial (Roux et al., 2017), among others since supplementary knowledge could be gained. In addition, it would be valuable to obtain more proactive transparency from the steering committee. This could indirectly contribute to stakeholder motivation (Onukwulu et al., 2025).

In the GDPS, certain signatories lacked substantial commitment. The potential barriers identified were time and resources, lack of clear added value, the need for more short-term objectives, and that the GDPS was limited to the Flemish region. The results also underscored the complexities involved in cultivating a shared sense of accountability and responsibility within a large-scale, multi-stakeholder transition initiative like the GDPS. There were also challenges of effectively communicating such initiatives internally and highlighted the importance of fostering a supportive organisational culture around Sustainable Development Goals. The possibility of reducing barriers for substantial commitments could be further investigated. Literature also suggests that stakeholders' expectations should be realistic, aligned with the scope of the initiative, clearly delineated in collaboration with all stakeholder groups. This approach helps to establish realistic expectations and prevent misunderstandings and frustrations (Lang et al., 2012; Luyet et al., 2012; Reed, 2008; Wiek et al., 2012).

One can conclude valuable intermediate **outcomes** of the GDPS. Most signatories felt jointly responsible for the outcomes and value them. There were also indications for social learning. Furthermore, there was increased capacity building and knowledge. The reasons to participate in the GDPS mostly aligned with these improvements. Since gaining systems knowledge was not a major reason for signatories to participate, there was no gap identified by them. However, according to transition theory (Pohl & Hirsch Hadorn, 2007), it would be beneficial if more extended knowledge from the GDPS about the current Flemish food environment was shared. Some signatories would also benefit from more input about the issues related to current Flemish protein overconsumption. In addition, considering a rather big group could have been learning more and thinks it was important to learn more about transformation knowledge, there was an interesting opportunity for improvement. This opportunity was already recently detected by the GDPS steering committee, since they expressed the wish to build

and share a system change theory about the protein transition in Flanders as an important next step. An online platform for document exchange could be utilised, a possibility that had not yet been explored.

Interesting impacts were recognised by signatories on organisational level. In most instances, the GDPS directly enhanced awareness about the environmental impact of food, stimulated conversation, reduced resistance and increased motivation for the protein transition. In addition, various actions were implemented that would not have occurred otherwise, both by signatories and potentially also outside the GDPS. The recognised impacts on consumer level regarding the GDPS twofold objective was limited. To ameliorate this, on the one hand, the 'halfhalf' communication could also be spread through official Flemish Government channels and consequently by various signatories in different languages, apart from 'Vlaams Instituut Gezond Leven'. Given the political rightward shift of society, the narrative could also focus more on personal health and away from ecological sustainability. On the other hand, also the food environment should be further adapted in favour of plant-based consumption (Herforth & Ahmed, 2015).

In this paper, a framework from transdisciplinary science was employed within a multi-actor partnership. Although the GDPS was not initially designed with the exact aims of transdisciplinary science, similar outcomes were nonetheless gained to varying extent. Our assessment validates and adds on the framework of Blackstock et al. (2007) and Hubeau et al. (2017), which proved useful in structuring our analysis. This paper contributed to a more nuanced understanding of the processes involved in multi-actor transition partnerships. These insights provide valuable guidance for policymakers, researchers, and other stakeholders seeking to strengthen the design and effectiveness of future multi-actor collaborations.

5 References

- Becker, J. (2004). Making sustainable development evaluations work. *Sustainable Development*, 12(4), 200–211. <https://doi.org/10.1002/sd.236>
- Blackstock, K. L., Kelly, G. J., & Horsey, B. L. (2007). Developing and applying a framework to evaluate participatory research for sustainability. *Ecological Economics*, 60(4), 726–742. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecolecon.2006.05.014>
- Bryson, J. M., Crosby, B. C., & Stone, M. M. (2006). The Design and Implementation of Cross-Sector Collaborations: Propositions from the Literature. *Public Administration Review*, 66(s1), 44–55. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1540-6210.2006.00665.x>
- Carley, M., & Christie, I. (2000). *Managing Sustainable Development*. Earthscan.
- De Ridder, K., Bel, S., Brocatus, L., Cuypers, K., Lebacqz, T., Moyersoen, I., Ost, C., & Teppers, E. (2016). *Voedselconsumptiepeiling 2014-2015. Rapport 4: De consumptie van voedingsmiddelen en de inname van voedingsstoffen*. WIV-ISP. <https://www.sciensano.be/nl/biblio/voedselconsumptiepeiling-2014-2015-rapport-4-de-consumptie-van-voedingsmiddelen-en-de-inname-van>
- Departement Omgeving. (2021). *Green Deal Eiwitshift op ons bord Initiatierapport*. https://omgeving.vlaanderen.be/sites/default/files/2021-11/Green%20Deal%20Eiwitshift_tekst.pdf
- Departement Omgeving. (2022). *Green Deal Eiwitshift op ons bord Voortgangsrapport 1* (p. 38). Vlaamse Overheid. https://omgeving.vlaanderen.be/sites/default/files/2022-05/2022_GD_Eiwitshift_Voortgangsrapportage1_final.pdf
- Departement Omgeving. (2023a). *Green Deal Eiwitshift op ons bord Bouwblokken voedselroutines*. Vlaamse Overheid. https://omgeving.vlaanderen.be/sites/default/files/2023-09/GDEiwitshift_rapport_werkgroepen.pdf
- Departement Omgeving. (2023b). *Green Deal Eiwitshift op ons bord Voortgangsrapport 2* (p. 69). Vlaamse Overheid. https://omgeving.vlaanderen.be/sites/default/files/2023-09/2023_GD_Eiwitshift_Voortgangsrapportage%20jaar%202.pdf
- Departement Omgeving. (2024a). *Green Deal Duurzame Zorg*. <https://omgeving.vlaanderen.be/nl/013-duurzame-zorg>
- Departement Omgeving. (2024b). *Green Deal Eiwitshift op ons bord*. <https://omgeving.vlaanderen.be/nl/010-eiwitshift-op-ons-bord>
- Departement Omgeving. (2024c). *Green Deal Eiwitshift op ons bord Voortgangsrapport 3*. Vlaamse Overheid. https://omgeving.vlaanderen.paddlecms.net/sites/default/files/2024-06/2024_GD_Eiwitshift_voortgangsrapportage_jaar3_final.pdf
- Departement Omgeving. (2024d). *Green Deals in Vlaanderen*. <https://omgeving.vlaanderen.be/nl/greendeal>
- Frame, B. (2008). 'Wicked', 'Messy', and 'Clumsy': Long-Term Frameworks for Sustainability. *Environment and Planning C: Government and Policy*, 26(6), 1113–1128. <https://doi.org/10.1068/c0790s>
- Herforth, A., & Ahmed, S. (2015). The food environment, its effects on dietary consumption, and potential for measurement within agriculture-nutrition interventions. *Food Security*, 7(3), 505–520. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12571-015-0455-8>
- Hubeau, M., Marchand, F., Coteur, I., Debruyne, L., & Van Huylenbroeck, G. (2017). A reflexive assessment of a regional initiative in the agri-food system to test whether and how it meets the premises of transdisciplinary research. *Sustainability Science*, 13(4), 1137–1154. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11625-017-0514-5>
- Lang, D. J., Wiek, A., Bergmann, M., Stauffacher, M., Martens, P., Moll, P., Swilling, M., & Thomas, C. J. (2012). Transdisciplinary research in sustainability science: Practice, principles, and challenges. *Sustainability Science*, 7(SUPPL. 1), 25–43. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11625-011-0149-x>
- Luyet, V., Schlaepfer, R., Parlange, M. B., & Buttler, A. (2012). A framework to implement Stakeholder participation in environmental projects. *Journal of Environmental Management*, 111, 213–219. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jenvman.2012.06.026>
- Onukwulu, E. C., Dienagha, I. N., Digitemie, W. N., Egbumokei, P. I., & Oladipo, O. T. (2025). Enhancing Sustainability through Stakeholder Engagement: Strategies for Effective Circular Economy Practices. *South Asian Journal of Social Studies and Economics*, 22(1), 135–150. <https://doi.org/10.9734/sajsse/2025/v22i1950>
- Pohl, C., & Hirsch Hadorn, G. (2007). *Principles for Designing Transdisciplinary Research*. oekom verlag. <https://doi.org/10.14512/9783962388638>
- Reed, M. S. (2008). Stakeholder participation for environmental management: A literature review. *Biological Conservation*, 141(10), 2417–2431. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biocon.2008.07.014>

- Rittel, H. W. J., & Webber, M. M. (1973). Dilemmas in a general theory of planning. *Policy Sciences*, 4(2), 155–169. <https://doi.org/10.1007/BF01405730>
- Roux, D. J., Nel, J. L., Cundill, G., O'Farrell, P., & Fabricius, C. (2017). Transdisciplinary research for systemic change: Who to learn with, what to learn about and how to learn. *Sustainability Science*, 12(5), 711–726. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11625-017-0446-0>
- Rubens, K., Wynants, E., Moyersoen, I., Guffens, L., & Michiels, K. (2024). *EI-MEET: monitoring eiwitname en -aankopen in Vlaanderen* (p. 72). https://archieff.algemeen.omgeving.vlaanderen.be/xmlui/bitstream/handle/acd/1000885/2023_eimeet_monitoring_eiwitshift_vlaanderen_finaal.pdf
- Schneider, F., Giger, M., Harari, N., Moser, S., Oberlack, C., Providoli, I., Schmid, L., Tribaldos, T., & Zimmermann, A. (2019). Transdisciplinary co-production of knowledge and sustainability transformations: Three generic mechanisms of impact generation. *Environmental Science & Policy*, 102, 26–35. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envsci.2019.08.017>
- Wiek, A., Ness, B., Schweizer-Ries, P., Brand, F. S., & Farioli, F. (2012). From complex systems analysis to transformational change: A comparative appraisal of sustainability science projects. *Sustainability Science*, 7(1), 5–24. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11625-011-0148-y>

6 Appendices

Appendix 1: Table with questions of the interviews and questionnaire, linked to the evaluation criteria

(the questions were asked to all respondents, unless specified)

Evaluation criteria	Questions of the interviews	Questions of the questionnaire
Initiation	<p>“Welke reacties kregen jullie van andere organisaties op jullie deelname aan de Green Deal Eiwitshift? Kan je enkele voorbeelden van reacties geven?”</p> <p>“Welke reacties kregen jullie binnen jullie organisatie op jullie deelname aan de Green Deal Eiwitshift? Kan je enkele voorbeelden van reacties geven?”</p> <p>Probing for both: Waren er ook andere negatieve/positieve voorbeelden?</p> <p>Mag ik deze reacties dus benoemen als uitsluitend negatief / vooral negatief / neutraal / vooral positief / uitsluitend positief?</p> <p><u>To GDPS initiators only:</u></p> <p>“Hoe is de Green Deal Eiwitshift tot stand gekomen? Welke beslissingen werden genomen en welke stakeholders waren daarbij betrokken?”</p> <p>“Hoe hebben organisaties zich aangesloten? Werden deze door jullie (Dep. Omgeving/andere initiatiefnemers /stuurgroepen) gecontacteerd of hebben organisaties zichzelf aangemeld?”</p>	<p>“Welke soort reacties kregen jullie van andere organisaties op jullie deelname aan de Green Deal Eiwitshift?” [uitsluitend negatief / vooral negatief / neutraal / vooral positief / uitsluitend positief / geen idee]</p> <p>“Wat waren deze reacties van andere organisaties?” [open veld, non-obligatory]</p> <p>“Welke soort reacties kregen jullie binnen jullie organisatie op jullie deelname aan de Green Deal Eiwitshift?” [uitsluitend negatief / vooral negatief / neutraal / vooral positief / uitsluitend positief / geen idee]</p> <p>“Wat waren deze reacties binnen jullie organisatie?” [open veld, non-obligatory]</p>
Institutional context	<p>“Vinden jullie het als organisatie positief dat het ondertekenen van de Green Deal Eiwitshift een inspanningsverbintenis is en geen resultaatsverbintenis?”</p> <p>Probing: Zou je dit willen toelichten?</p>	<p>In hoeverre gaat jullie organisatie akkoord met deze stelling: [helemaal oneens / oneens / neutraal / eens / helemaal eens / geen idee]</p> <p>“Wij als organisatie vinden het positief dat het ondertekenen van de Green Deal Eiwitshift een inspanningsverbintenis is en geen resultaatsverbintenis.”</p> <p>“Hoe merken jullie dat? Waarom precies?” [open veld, non-obligatory]</p>
Leadership	<p>“Is de rolverdeling binnen de Green Deal Eiwitshift duidelijk?”</p> <p>“Is de rolverdeling binnen de Green Deal Eiwitshift zoals gewenst?”</p> <p>“Zijn de machtsverhoudingen binnen de Green Deal Eiwitshift zoals gewenst?”</p> <p>Probing for all three: Zou je dit willen toelichten? Hoe merken jullie dat? Kan je een voorbeeld geven?</p>	<p>In hoeverre gaat jullie organisatie akkoord met deze stellingen: [helemaal oneens / oneens / neutraal / eens / helemaal eens / geen idee]</p> <p>“De rolverdeling binnen de Green Deal Eiwitshift is duidelijk (ondertekenaars versus stuurgroep).”</p> <p>“De rolverdeling binnen de Green Deal Eiwitshift is zoals gewenst (ondertekenaars versus stuurgroep).”</p> <p>“De machtsverhoudingen binnen de Green Deal Eiwitshift zijn zoals gewenst (ondertekenaars versus stuurgroep).”</p> <p>“Hoe merken jullie dat? Waarom precies?” [open veld, non-obligatory]</p>
Internal communication	<p>“Is er voldoende informatie-uitwisseling van de stuurgroep naar de ondertekenaars?”</p> <p>“Is er voldoende informatie-uitwisseling van de ondertekenaars naar de stuurgroep?”</p> <p>“Is de inhoud van de informatie-uitwisseling binnen de Green Deal Eiwitshift relevant voor het behalen van de doelstellingen?”</p> <p>Probing for all three: Zou je dit willen toelichten? Hoe merken jullie dat? Kan je een voorbeeld geven?</p>	<p>In hoeverre gaat jullie organisatie akkoord met deze stellingen: [helemaal oneens / oneens / neutraal / eens / helemaal eens / geen idee]</p> <p>“Er is voldoende informatie-uitwisseling van de stuurgroep naar de ondertekenaars.”</p> <p>“Er is voldoende informatie-uitwisseling van de ondertekenaars naar de stuurgroep.”</p> <p>“De inhoud van de informatie-uitwisseling binnen de Green Deal Eiwitshift is relevant voor het behalen van de doelstellingen.”</p>
Transparency	<p>“Begrijpt jullie organisatie de redenering achter de beslissingen die zijn genomen in de Green Deal Eiwitshift?”</p> <p>“Is er voldoende transparantie over de uiteindelijke beslissingen door de stuurgroep?”</p>	<p>In hoeverre gaat jullie organisatie akkoord met deze stellingen: [helemaal oneens / oneens / neutraal / eens / helemaal eens / geen idee]</p> <p>“Onze organisatie begrijpt de redenering achter de beslissingen die zijn genomen in de Green Deal Eiwitshift.”</p> <p>“De stuurgroep is voldoende transparant over de uiteindelijke beslissingen.”</p>

	Probing for both: Zou je dit willen toelichten? Hoe merken jullie dat? Kan je een voorbeeld geven?	“Hoe merken jullie dat? Waarom precies?” [open veld, non-obligatory]
Representation	<p>“Is iedereen welkom bij de Green Deal Eiwitshift?”</p> <p>“Ervaren jullie bij de Green Deal Eiwitshift een veilige open sfeer?”</p> <p>“Zijn de verschillende organisaties die nodig zijn om de doelstellingen te bereiken, betrokken bij de Green Deal Eiwitshift?”</p> <p>[Enkel indien (helemaal) oneens / neutraal]: “Welke organisaties zouden nog betrokken moeten worden?”</p> <p>Probing for all three: Zou je dit willen toelichten? Hoe merken jullie dat? Kan je een voorbeeld geven?</p>	<p>In hoeverre gaat jullie organisatie akkoord met deze stellingen: [helemaal oneens / oneens / neutraal / eens / helemaal eens / geen idee]</p> <p>“Bij de Green Deal Eiwitshift is iedereen welkom.”</p> <p>“Bij de Green Deal Eiwitshift ervaren we een veilige open sfeer.”</p> <p>“De verschillende organisaties die nodig zijn om de doelstellingen te bereiken, zijn betrokken bij de Green Deal Eiwitshift.”</p> <p>“Welke organisatie(s) zou(den) nog betrokken moeten worden?”</p> <p>“Hoe merken jullie dat? Waarom precies?” [open veld, non-obligatory]</p>
Conflict resolution	<p>“Waren er vaak meningsverschillen tussen ondertekenaars en/of stuurgroepleden?”</p> <p>Probing: Mag ik het dus beschrijven als nooit / zelden / soms / vaak / heel vaak?</p> <p>[Enkel indien geen “nooit”] “Hoe tevreden zijn jullie over de manier waarop wordt omgegaan met deze meningsverschillen?”</p> <p>Probing: Mag ik het dus beschrijven als zeer ontevreden / enigszins ontevreden / neutraal / enigszins tevreden / zeer tevreden?</p> <p>Kan je enkele voorbeelden geven?</p> <p><u>To steering members only:</u></p> <p>“Een aantal ondertekenaars hebben hun deelname stopgezet. Wat was de aanleiding hiervan? Hoe hebben jullie dit ervaren?”</p> <p>Probing: Hebben jullie dit ervaren als een conflict?</p>	<p>“Hoe vaak waren er meningsverschillen tussen ondertekenaars en/of stuurgroepleden?” [Nooit / zelden / soms / vaak / heel vaak / geen idee]</p> <p>[Enkel indien geen “nooit”]</p> <p>“Hoe tevreden zijn jullie over de manier waarop werd omgegaan met deze meningsverschillen?” [Zeer ontevreden / enigszins ontevreden / neutraal / enigszins tevreden / zeer tevreden / geen idee]</p> <p>“Wat waren deze meningsverschillen en hoe werd daarmee omgegaan?” (overlap "internal communication") [open veld, non-obligatory]</p> <p><u>To steering members only:</u></p> <p>“Een aantal ondertekenaars hebben hun deelname stopgezet. Wat was de aanleiding hiervan? Hebben jullie dit ervaren als een conflict?” (overlap "internal communication") [open veld]</p>
Influence on the process	<p>“Wanneer jullie een standpunt deelden, heeft dit invloed gehad op de Green Deal Eiwitshift?”</p> <p>“Wanneer jullie kennis deelden, heeft dit invloed gehad op de Green Deal Eiwitshift?”</p> <p>Probing for both: Zou je dit willen toelichten? Hoe merken jullie dat? Kan je een voorbeeld geven?</p>	<p>In hoeverre gaat jullie organisatie akkoord met deze stellingen: [helemaal oneens / oneens / neutraal / eens / helemaal eens / geen idee / NVT, we hebben geen standpunt of kennis gedeeld]</p> <p>“Wanneer we een standpunt deelden, heeft dit invloed gehad op de Green Deal Eiwitshift. (overlap "representation")</p> <p>“Wanneer we kennis deelden, heeft dit invloed gehad op de Green Deal Eiwitshift.</p>
Accountability	<p>“Voelt jullie organisatie zich intussen mee verantwoordelijk voor de resultaten van de Green Deal Eiwitshift?”</p> <p>“Vindt jullie organisatie de resultaten van de Green Deal Eiwitshift waardevol?”</p> <p>Probing for both: Zou je dit willen toelichten? Hoe merken jullie dat? Kan je een voorbeeld geven?</p>	<p>In hoeverre gaat jullie organisatie akkoord met deze stellingen: [helemaal oneens / oneens / neutraal / eens / helemaal eens / geen idee]</p> <p>“Intussen voelt onze organisatie zich mee verantwoordelijk voor de resultaten van de Green Deal Eiwitshift.”</p> <p>“Onze organisatie vindt de resultaten van de Green Deal Eiwitshift waardevol.”</p> <p>“Hoe merken jullie dat? Waarom precies?” [open veld, non-obligatory]</p>
Capacity building	<p>“Heeft jullie deelname aan de Green Deal Eiwitshift jullie vaardigheden (zoals communicatieve en empathische) verbeterd om deel te nemen aan toekomstige samenwerkingen?”</p> <p>Probing: Zou je dit willen toelichten? Hoe merken jullie dat? Kan je een voorbeeld geven?”</p> <p>“Was vaardigheden verbeteren een belangrijke reden voor jullie organisatie om deel te nemen aan de Green Deal Eiwitshift?”</p>	<p>In hoeverre gaat jullie organisatie akkoord met deze stelling: [helemaal oneens / oneens / neutraal / eens / helemaal eens / geen idee / NVT, onze vaardigheden waren al optimaal] “Onze deelname aan de Green Deal Eiwitshift heeft onze vaardigheden (zoals communicatieve en empathische) verbeterd om deel te nemen aan toekomstige samenwerkingen.” (overlap "social learning")</p> <p>“Hoe merken jullie dat? Waarom precies?” [open veld, non-obligatory]</p>

	<p>“Heeft jullie deelname aan de Green Deal Eiwitshift geleid tot nieuwe of verdiepte professionele connecties die in de toekomst tot samenwerkingen kunnen leiden?” Probing: Zou je dit willen toelichten? Hoe merken jullie dat? Kan je een voorbeeld geven? “Waren die connecties leggen een belangrijke reden voor jullie organisatie om deel te nemen aan de Green Deal Eiwitshift?”</p> <p>“Kunnen jullie door jullie deelname aan de Green Deal Eiwitshift de complexiteit van de eiwitshift beter begrijpen?” Probing: Zou je dit willen toelichten? Hoe merken jullie dat? Kan je een voorbeeld geven? “Was de complexiteit van de eiwitshift begrijpen een belangrijke reden voor jullie organisatie om deel te nemen aan de Green Deal Eiwitshift?”</p>	<p>“Hoe belangrijk was het verbeteren van jullie vaardigheden als reden voor jullie organisatie om deel te nemen aan de Green Deal Eiwitshift?” [Onbelangrijk / enigszins onbelangrijk / neutraal / enigszins belangrijk / belangrijk / geen idee]</p> <p>In hoeverre gaat jullie organisatie akkoord met deze stelling: [helemaal oneens / oneens / neutraal / eens / helemaal eens / geen idee / NVT, onze connecties waren al optimaal] “Onze deelname aan de Green Deal Eiwitshift heeft geleid tot nieuwe of verdiepte professionele connecties die in de toekomst tot samenwerkingen kunnen leiden.” (overlap "social learning") “Hoe merken jullie dat? Waarom precies?” [open veld, non-obligatory] “Hoe belangrijk was het bekomen of verdiepen van jullie connecties als reden voor jullie organisatie om deel te nemen aan de Green Deal Eiwitshift?” [Onbelangrijk / enigszins onbelangrijk / neutraal / enigszins belangrijk / belangrijk / geen idee]</p> <p>In hoeverre gaat jullie organisatie akkoord met deze stelling: [helemaal oneens / oneens / neutraal / eens / helemaal eens / geen idee / NVT, we begrepen de complexiteit al volledig] “Door onze deelname aan de Green Deal Eiwitshift kunnen we de complexiteit van de eiwitshift beter begrijpen.” (overlap "social learning") “Hoe merken jullie dat? Waarom precies?” [open veld, non-obligatory] “Hoe belangrijk was de complexiteit van de eiwitshift begrijpen als reden voor jullie organisatie om deel te nemen aan de Green Deal Eiwitshift?” [Onbelangrijk / enigszins onbelangrijk / neutraal / enigszins belangrijk / belangrijk / geen idee]</p>
<p>Knowledge</p>	<p>“Nu zal ik een reeks vragen stellen over hoeveel kennis jullie al dan niet hebben opgedaan door jullie deelname aan de Green Deal Eiwitshift: Hoeveel kennis hebben jullie opgedaan over de problemen met de huidige Vlaamse consumptie van dierlijke eiwitten?” (cfr. Systems knowledge) “Hoeveel kennis hebben jullie opgedaan over de problemen met de Vlaamse overconsumptie van eiwitten?” (cfr. Systems knowledge) “Hoeveel kennis hebben jullie opgedaan over de problemen met de huidige Vlaamse voedselomgeving? Dit omvat de beschikbaarheid, informatie, prijs, promotie en zichtbaarheid van voedselverkooppunten en voedingsmiddelen, maar ook de heersende sociale normen, voedselcultuur, voedselrichtlijnen en wetgeving.” (cfr. Systems knowledge) “Hoeveel kennis hebben jullie opgedaan over de gewenste Vlaamse eiwitshiftoekomst (halfhalf)?” (cfr. Target knowledge) “Hoeveel kennis hebben jullie opgedaan over de waarden en normen van de Vlaamse stakeholders over de eiwitshift?” (cfr. Target knowledge) “Hoeveel kennis hebben jullie opgedaan over de noodzakelijke stappen om de eiwitshift te realiseren in Vlaanderen?” (cfr. Transformation knowledge) Probing for all six: Zou je dit willen toelichten?</p>	<p>Hoeveel kennis heeft jullie organisatie opgedaan door jullie deelname aan de Green Deal Eiwitshift? [Geen kennis opgedaan / enigszins kennis opgedaan / voldoende kennis opgedaan / veel kennis opgedaan / uitgebreide kennis opgedaan / geen idee / NVT, we hadden hierover al veel kennis]</p> <p>–“Hoeveel kennis hebben jullie opgedaan over de problemen met de huidige Vlaamse consumptie van dierlijke eiwitten?” (cfr. Systems knowledge) –“Hoeveel kennis hebben jullie opgedaan over de problemen met de Vlaamse overconsumptie van eiwitten?” (cfr. Systems knowledge) –“Hoeveel kennis hebben jullie opgedaan over de problemen met de huidige Vlaamse voedselomgeving? DEF: omvat de beschikbaarheid, informatie, prijs, promotie en zichtbaarheid van voedselverkooppunten en voedingsmiddelen, maar ook de heersende sociale normen, voedselcultuur, voedselrichtlijnen en wetgeving.” (cfr. Systems knowledge) –“Hoeveel kennis hebben jullie opgedaan over de gewenste Vlaamse eiwitshiftoekomst (halfhalf)?” (cfr. Target knowledge) –“Hoeveel kennis hebben jullie opgedaan over de waarden en normen van de Vlaamse stakeholders over de eiwitshift?” (cfr. Target knowledge) (overlap "social learning")</p>

	<p>“Was kennis opdoen een belangrijke reden voor jullie organisatie om deel te nemen aan de Green Deal Eiwitshift? Zo ja, welke soort kennis?”</p>	<p>–“Hoeveel kennis hebben jullie opgedaan over de noodzakelijke stappen om de eiwitshift te realiseren in Vlaanderen?” (cfr. Transformation knowledge)</p> <p>Hoe belangrijk was kennis opdoen als reden voor jullie organisatie om deel te nemen aan de Green Deal Eiwitshift? [Onbelangrijk / enigszins onbelangrijk / neutraal / enigszins belangrijk / belangrijk / geen idee / NVT, we hadden hierover al veel kennis]</p> <p>–“Bijleren over de problemen met de huidige Vlaamse consumptie van dierlijke eiwitten”</p> <p>–“Bijleren over de problemen met de Vlaamse overconsumptie van eiwitten”</p> <p>–“Bijleren over de problemen met de huidige Vlaamse voedselomgeving”</p> <p>–“Bijleren over de gewenste Vlaamse eiwitshifttoekomst (halfhalf)”</p> <p>–“Bijleren over de waarden en normen van de Vlaamse stakeholders over de eiwitshift”</p> <p>–“Bijleren over de noodzakelijke stappen om de eiwitshift te realiseren in Vlaanderen”</p>
<p>Recognised impacts</p>	<p>“Heeft jullie betrokkenheid bij de Green Deal Eiwitshift het bewustzijn bij jullie organisatie vergroot in verband met de impact van voeding op het milieu?”</p> <p>“Heeft jullie betrokkenheid bij de Green Deal Eiwitshift ervoor gezorgd dat de eiwitshift meer bespreekbaar is in jullie organisatie?”</p> <p>“Heeft jullie betrokkenheid bij de Green Deal Eiwitshift ervoor gezorgd dat er minder weerstand is ten opzichte van de eiwitshift in jullie organisatie?”</p> <p>“Heeft jullie betrokkenheid bij de Green Deal Eiwitshift ervoor gezorgd dat er meer motivatie is bij jullie organisatie om de eiwitshift te versnellen?”</p> <p>“Heeft jullie betrokkenheid bij de Green Deal Eiwitshift gezorgd voor het uitvoeren van acties die anders niet zouden hebben plaatsgevonden bij jullie organisatie?”</p> <p>“Zijn meer Vlamingen van mening dat het normaal is om meer plantaardig te eten door de Green Deal Eiwitshift?”</p> <p>Probing for all six: Zou je dit willen toelichten? Hoe merken jullie dat? Kan je een voorbeeld geven?</p> <p>“Heeft de Green Deal Eiwitshift de verhouding tussen dierlijke en plantaardige eiwitten verbeterd in de Vlaamse consumptie?”</p> <p>“Heeft de Green Deal Eiwitshift een vermindering bekomen van de totale inname van eiwitten in de Vlaamse consumptie?”</p> <p>Probing for both: Zou je dit willen toelichten? Hoe merken jullie dat?</p> <p>“Even los van jullie organisatie, ken je andere activiteiten die niet binnen de Green Deal Eiwitshift georganiseerd zijn, maar ook zouden kunnen bijdragen aan de eiwitshift? Denk bijvoorbeeld aan een wedstrijd, media-aandacht, ... Zo ja, dewelke?”</p> <p>“Doet jullie organisatie nog andere activiteiten die zouden kunnen bijdragen aan de eiwitshift, naast wat beschreven is in de voortgangsrapportage en op de website van de Green Deal Eiwitshift? Zo ja, dewelke?”</p>	<p>In hoeverre gaat jullie organisatie akkoord met deze stellingen: [helemaal oneens / oneens / neutraal / eens / helemaal eens / geen idee]</p> <p>–“Onze betrokkenheid bij de Green Deal Eiwitshift heeft het bewustzijn bij onze organisatie vergroot in verband met de impact van voeding op het milieu.</p> <p>Extra optie: [NVT, ons bewustzijn was al optimaal]” (overlap "social learning")</p> <p>–“Onze betrokkenheid bij de Green Deal Eiwitshift heeft ervoor gezorgd dat de eiwitshift meer bespreekbaar is in onze organisatie.</p> <p>Extra optie: [NVT, het was al volledig bespreekbaar]”</p> <p>–“Onze betrokkenheid bij de Green Deal Eiwitshift heeft ervoor gezorgd dat er minder weerstand is ten opzichte van de eiwitshift in onze organisatie.</p> <p>Extra optie: [NVT, er was al geen weerstand meer]”</p> <p>–“Onze betrokkenheid bij de Green Deal Eiwitshift heeft ervoor gezorgd dat er meer motivatie is bij onze organisatie om de eiwitshift te versnellen.</p> <p>Extra optie: [NVT, er was al een optimale motivatie]”</p> <p>–“Onze betrokkenheid bij de Green Deal Eiwitshift heeft gezorgd voor het uitvoeren van acties die anders niet zouden hebben plaatsgevonden bij onze organisatie.”</p> <p>–“Door de Green Deal Eiwitshift zijn meer Vlamingen van mening dat het normaal is om meer plantaardig te eten.”</p> <p>–“Door de Green Deal Eiwitshift is de verhouding in de Vlaamse consumptie tussen dierlijke en plantaardige eiwitten gewijzigd in de bedeelde richting.”</p> <p>–“Door de Green Deal Eiwitshift is er een vermindering in de totale inname van eiwitten in Vlaanderen.”</p> <p>“Hoe merken jullie dat? Waarom precies?” [open veld, non-obligatory]</p> <p>“Even los van jullie organisatie: welke andere activiteiten kennen jullie die niet binnen de Green Deal Eiwitshift georganiseerd zijn, maar ook zouden</p>

		kunnen bijdragen aan de eiwitshifft? Denk bijvoorbeeld aan een wedstrijd, media-aandacht, ..." [open veld, non-obligatory] "Doet jullie organisatie nog andere activiteiten die zouden kunnen bijdragen aan de eiwitshifft, naast wat beschreven is in de voortgangsrapportage en op de website van de Green Deal Eiwitshifft?" [Nee, alles staat reeds beschreven]/[Ja, namelijk...]
Social learning	"Heeft jullie organisatie door jullie betrokkenheid bij de Green Deal Eiwitshifft bijgeleerd over de kennis en ervaring van anderen in het voedselsysteem?" Probing: Zou je dit willen toelichten? Hoe merken jullie dat? Kan je een voorbeeld geven?	In hoeverre gaat jullie organisatie akkoord met deze stelling: [helemaal oneens / oneens / neutraal / eens / helemaal eens / geen idee] "Door onze betrokkenheid bij de Green Deal Eiwitshifft heeft onze organisatie bijgeleerd over de kennis en ervaring van anderen in het voedselsysteem." (overlap "knowledge") "Hoe merken jullie dat? Waarom precies?" [open veld, non-obligatory]
Extra questions to capture more insights	"Wat zouden jullie graag veranderen aan de Green Deal Eiwitshifft (doelstellingen, werkvormen, ...)? Is er iets wat jullie zou kunnen helpen om nog meer betrokken te zijn bij de Green Deal Eiwitshifft?" "Wat zouden jullie adviseren aan iemand die probeert een vergelijkbaar samenwerkingsverband te ontwikkelen?" "Hoe zou volgens jullie de eiwitshifft versneld kunnen worden?" "Is er nog iets anders dat je belangrijk vindt om te vermelden?" Probe: Heb je nog vragen en/of bemerkingen over jouw antwoorden, het onderzoek en/of over de Green Deal Eiwitshifft?	"Wat zouden jullie graag veranderen aan de Green Deal Eiwitshifft (doelstellingen, werkvormen, ...)? Is er iets wat jullie zou kunnen helpen om nog meer betrokken te zijn bij de Green Deal Eiwitshifft?" [open veld, non-obligatory] "Wat zouden jullie adviseren aan iemand die probeert een vergelijkbaar samenwerkingsverband te ontwikkelen?" [open veld, non-obligatory] "Hoe zou volgens jullie de eiwitshifft versneld kunnen worden?" [open veld, non-obligatory]
Background information on respondents and signatory	"... (naam organisatie) heeft de Green Deal Eiwitshifft ondertekend in ... (jaartal), vanaf welk jaar was je persoonlijk betrokken bij de Green Deal Eiwitshifft?" [antwoord moet tussen 2021 en 2024 zijn] "Was er een periode waarin je tijdelijk niet betrokken was?" "Wat is jouw persoonlijke rol binnen de Green Deal Eiwitshifft?" Probing: Was je ook ooit stuurgroep lid? Was je ook coördinator of uitvoerder voor de implementatie van de gedefinieerde acties van jullie organisatie? "Hoe vaak was jullie organisatie aanwezig op de groepsactiviteiten van de Green Deal Eiwitshifft (plenaire bijeenkomsten, workshops, webinars, ...)?" "Wat is jouw leeftijd?"	"Wat is de naam van jullie organisatie?" [open veld] "In welk jaar heeft jullie organisatie de Green Deal Eiwitshifft ondertekend?" [Bij de start, dus tegen april 2021 / 2022 / 2023 / 2024] "Vanaf welk jaar was u persoonlijk betrokken bij de Green Deal Eiwitshifft?" [Bij de start, dus tegen april 2021 / 2022 / 2023 / 2024] "Was u binnen deze periode tijdelijk even niet betrokken bij de Green Deal Eiwitshifft?" [Nee, ik was vanaf de aangegeven periode ononderbroken betrokken. / Ja, ik was tijdelijk even niet betrokken, namelijk in de periode van ...] "Wat is uw persoonlijke rol binnen de Green Deal Eiwitshifft?" [Stuurgroep lid / Coördinator voor de implementatie van de gedefinieerde acties van onze organisatie / Uitvoerder van de gedefinieerde acties van onze organisatie] "Hoe vaak was jullie organisatie aanwezig op de groepsactiviteiten van de Green Deal Eiwitshifft (plenaire bijeenkomsten, workshops, webinars, ...)?" [Nooit / zelden / soms / vaak / altijd / geen idee] "Wat is uw eigen leeftijd?" [18-70, non-obligatory]

Appendix 2: Ethics documents

Geïnfomeerde toestemming

Titel van het onderzoek:

Ervaringen Green Deal 'Eiwitshift op ons bord' als project

Contactgegevens:

Erik Mathijs (coördinator Futures4Food): erik.mathijs@kuleuven.be

Ines Cottignie (contactpersoon KU Leuven - Futures4Food): ines.cottignie@kuleuven.be

KU Leuven Faculteit Bio-ingenieurswetenschappen

Departementen Aard- en Omgevingswetenschappen, Divisie Bio-economie

Celestijnenlaan 200E – box 2411, 3001 Leuven-Heverlee

Caroline Amrom (contactpersoon UCLouvain - Futures4Food): caroline.amrom@uclouvain.be

SYTRA - 2, Croix du Sud, 1348 Louvain-La-Neuve

Doel en methodologie van het onderzoek:

Inzicht krijgen in de Vlaamse Green Deal 'Eiwitshift op ons bord' als project ter realisatie van de eiwitshift. Uit de bevragingen van de ondertekenaars en stuurgroep van deze Green Deal kunnen de gegevens worden gebruikt om met wetenschappelijke neutraliteit inzicht te krijgen in deze Green Deal en om aanbevelingen af te leiden voor deze en andere projecten.

Duur van het experiment:

Lente-zomer 2024

- Ik heb voldoende tijd gehad om de informatie horende bij deze geïnformeerde toestemming door te nemen.
- Ik begrijp dat van mij verwacht wordt eerlijk te antwoorden op de vragen.
- Mijn deelname levert een bijdrage aan het wetenschappelijk onderzoek. Ik weet dat ik geen compensatie voor mijn deelname zal ontvangen.
- Ik begrijp dat mijn deelname aan deze studie vrijwillig is. Ik heb het recht om mijn deelname op elk moment stop te zetten. Daarvoor hoef ik geen reden te geven en ik weet dat daaruit geen nadeel voor mij kan ontstaan.
- De resultaten van dit onderzoek kunnen gebruikt worden voor wetenschappelijke doeleinden en mogen gepubliceerd worden. Mijn naam wordt daarbij niet gepubliceerd, anonimiteit en de vertrouwelijkheid van de gegevens is in elk stadium van het onderzoek gewaarborgd.
- Mijn persoonsgegevens zullen verwerkt worden in lijn met de Algemene Verordening Gegevensbescherming (AVG/GDPR). Hierbij worden alleen de gegevens verwerkt die strikt noodzakelijk zijn voor het behalen van de onderzoeksdoelstellingen. Doorheen het onderzoek zullen mijn gegevens steeds vertrouwelijk behandeld worden. De onderzoekers nemen maatregelen om mijn privacy te beschermen. Mijn naam wordt niet gevraagd. Meer informatie over de verwerking van mijn persoonsgegevens kan teruggevonden worden in de bijgevoegde informatiebrief.
- Indien ik op de hoogte gehouden wil worden van de resultaten van dit onderzoek, contacteer ik ines.cottignie@kuleuven.be. Mijn e-mailadres wordt niet gekoppeld aan mijn antwoorden op de bevraging.
- Voor verdere vragen over het onderzoek, evenals voor de uitoefening van mijn rechten (inzage gegevens, correctie ervan,...), weet ik dat ik na mijn deelname terecht kan bij
Ines Cottignie ines.cottignie@kuleuven.be (contactpersoon KU Leuven – Futures4Food)
Caroline Amrom: caroline.amrom@uclouvain.be (contactpersoon UCLouvain - Futures4Food)

Verdere vragen over privacyaspecten kan ik me richten tot de data protection officer:

michele.remy@uclouvain.be

- Deze studie werd beoordeeld en goedgekeurd door "Comité d'éthique" van UCLouvain en is erkend bij KU Leuven onder dossiernummer G-2021-4619. Voor eventuele klachten of andere bezorgdheden omtrent ethische aspecten van deze studie kan ik contact opnemen met demande-ethique-ipsy@uclouvain.be

Door middel van mijn handtekening, verklaar ik hierbij zowel de informatiebrief over de verwerking van mijn persoonsgegevens als deze geïnformeerde toestemming te hebben gelezen en begrepen. Ik heb antwoord gekregen op al mijn vragen betreffende deze studie. Ik stem toe om deel te nemen.

Naam:

Datum:

Handtekening:

Informatiebrief over de verwerking van mijn persoonsgegevens Ervaringen Green Deal 'Eiwitshift op ons bord' als project

DOEL EN METHODOLOGIE VAN HET ONDERZOEK

Inzicht krijgen in de Vlaamse Green Deal 'Eiwitshift op ons bord' als project ter realisatie van de eiwitshift. Uit de bevragingen van de ondertekenaars en stuurgroep van deze Green Deal kunnen de gegevens worden gebruikt om met wetenschappelijke neutraliteit inzicht te krijgen in deze Green Deal en om aanbevelingen af te leiden voor deze en andere projecten.

INFORMATIE OVER DE VERWERKING VAN UW GEGEVENS

In het kader van uw deelname aan dit onderzoek zullen gegevens over u verzameld en verwerkt worden. Deze verwerking zal gebeuren in overeenstemming met de Algemene Verordening Gegevensbescherming (AVG). Hierbij geven we u graag meer informatie over het gebruik en de bewaring van deze gegevens. In volgende alinea's vindt u meer informatie over de categorieën van gegevens die over u zullen verzameld worden tijdens dit onderzoek. Deze omvatten geen persoonsgegevens waaraan u geïdentificeerd zal kunnen worden zoals naam, adres, contact gegevens (bvb. E-mailadres), log(-in) data, etc. Deze omvatten wel persoonlijke gegevens zoals leeftijd.

Gebruik van uw gegevens

Enkel gegevens die noodzakelijk zijn voor de doeleinden van dit onderzoek zullen verzameld en verwerkt worden. Het onderzoek is met name gericht op de ervaringen met betrekking tot de Vlaamse Green Deal 'Eiwitshift op ons bord' van de ondertekenaars en de stuurgroep. De verzamelde gegevens en data kunnen mogelijks opnieuw gebruikt worden in het kader van toekomstig wetenschappelijk onderzoek. Uw gegevens zullen in het kader van dit onderzoek anoniem zijn. Dit wil zeggen dat er geen gegevens gevraagd worden die u kunnen identificeren zoals bijvoorbeeld uw naam of adres. In plaats daarvan krijgt u een unieke, willekeurige code. Ook in de wetenschappelijke output van dit onderzoek, zoals publicaties, zal u niet geïdentificeerd worden. Als wettelijke basis voor de verwerking van uw gegevens wordt het algemeen belang aangewend. Dit betekent dat het onderzoek zal leiden tot een vermeerdering van kennis en inzicht die de maatschappij (direct of indirect) ten goede komt. Uw gegevens zullen door de onderzoekers gedurende 10 jaar na afloop van het onderzoek bewaard worden op een beveiligde opslaglocatie van UCLouvain en/of KU Leuven. Na deze periode zullen de gegevens definitief verwijderd worden indien ze niet meer noodzakelijk zijn voor de uitvoering van het onderzoek.

Uw rechten

U hebt steeds het recht om meer informatie te vragen over het gebruik van uw gegevens. Daarnaast kan u beroep doen op het recht van inzage, het recht op verbetering (rectificatie) en het recht op verwijderen van uw gegevens voor zover deze rechten de doeleinden van het onderzoek niet onmogelijk maken of ernstig belemmeren. Indien u op één van deze rechten beroep wil doen, kan u contact opnemen met de onderzoekers aan de hand van de contactgegevens aan het einde van deze brief.

Andere ontvangers van uw data

Uw persoonsgegevens zullen niet worden doorgegeven aan derden.

Contactgegevens

UCLouvain fungeert als verwerkingsverantwoordelijke in het kader van dit onderzoek. Meer specifiek zullen enkel de onderzoekers Ines Cottignie en Caroline Amrom toegang hebben tot uw gegevens. Ingeval van specifieke vragen over dit onderzoek inclusief de verwerking van uw gegevens kan u met hen contact opnemen via de volgende informatie:

- Ines Cottignie: ines.cottignie@kuleuven.be (contactpersoon KU Leuven – Futures4Food)
- Caroline Amrom: caroline.amrom@uclouvain.be (contactpersoon UCLouvain – Futures4Food)

Voor verdere vragen en bedenkingen over de verwerking van uw persoonsgegevens kan u contact opnemen met de functionaris voor gegevensbescherming voor wetenschappelijk onderzoek van UCLouvain (michele.remy@uclouvain.be). Gelieve hierbij te verduidelijken om welk onderzoek het gaat door vermelding van de titel en de namen van de onderzoekers.

Indien u, na contact te hebben opgenomen met de functionaris voor gegevensbescherming, een klacht zou willen indienen over hoe uw informatie wordt behandeld, kan u terecht bij de Belgische Gegevensbeschermingsautoriteit (www.gegevensbeschermingsautoriteit.be).

Appendix 3: Timeline including the most important GDPS milestones

- 2021/04/26: start of GDPS incl. launch website
- 2021/05/31: online plenary meeting with signatories
- 2021/11/25: online webinar about behavioural insights for plant-based diets, talk by Behaven
- 2022/02/21: online plenary meeting with signatories
- 2022/06-2023/02: working groups building blocks
- 2022/10/21: conference 'Eiwitshift in Vlaanderen' about trends, innovations and positioning
- 2022/12/06: physical plenary meeting with signatories
- 2022/06/20-2023/01/24: 'halfhalf' narrative development
- 2022/06/31: physical plenary meeting with signatories
- 2023/05/14: physical plenary meeting with signatories
- 2023/11/06: physical plenary meeting with signatories
- 2023/11/14-2023/12/12: 'halfhalf' communication campaign incl. website
- 2024/02/13: monitoring report 'EI-MEET' published
- 2024/04/30: online webinar "The Danes lead the way - how Denmark is ramping up its efforts towards the protein shift", talk by Rune-Christoffer Dragsdahl from the Danish Vegetarian Society, Jessica Aschemann-Witzel from Aarhus University, Evelien Decuypere of the Flemish Agency for Agriculture and Fisheries, Vincent Smets of ProVeg Belgium/Next Food Chain and Erik Mathijs from KU Leuven
- 2024/05/14: physical plenary meeting with signatories
- 2024/06/18: online webinar "crisis consumption & True Cost of food", talk by Titus Ghyselincx of WWF and Pierre-Alexandre Billiet of Gondola
- 2024/05/24-2024/07/08: 7 semi-structured face-to-face interviews
- 2024/06/19-2024/08/11: 28 complete and valid questionnaire responses

Appendix 4: Amount of signatories responding to the interview or questionnaire and in total involved in the GDPS, per stakeholder category

Category	Amount of responding signatories (n=33)	Total amount of signatories in GDPS (n=84)
Supplier of agricultural necessities (B2B)	0	1
Farmer	0	1
Suppliers of ingredients (B2B)	1	2
Food processing companies (including those processing purely plant-based or hybrid foods)	3	19
Food wholesalers (B2B)	1	2
Non-food companies also providing catering for customers/employees	0	2
Healthcare institution	0	1
Caterers	1	4
Higher education and research institutes	4	9
Secondary school with food education	1	1
Supermarket chains	3	7
Food delivery company	0	1
Government institutions at Region or Community level	3	8
Government institution at Province level	1	1
Cities	5	6
Companies providing support/services to food stakeholders	1	4
Nonprofit organisations providing support/services to food stakeholders	9	15

Appendix 5: Principles endorsed by the GDPS signatories

1. “The Green Deal is important for strengthening the protein shift at the level of consumption.”
2. “We aim for a tasty, affordable, sustainable, healthy, and balanced diet with a better ratio between animal and plant-based proteins, including those from alternative sources, while respecting Belgian food culture and creating opportunities for local economic development and innovation.”
3. “We start from an inspiring and positive narrative, ensuring that the partners align with the objectives.”
4. “The participating parties commit to undertaking concrete and measurable actions.”
5. “We seek to increase public support for the protein shift. To this end, we present a clear goal and a unified message, while also considering the diversity within society and among the group of partners.”
6. “The actions in this Green Deal contribute to its objective.”
7. “Through this Green Deal, we are already addressing long-term goals. Both short- and long-term objectives are important for this collaboration, with the long-term serving as a guiding focus.”
8. “A protein shift aims to achieve benefits in terms of the environment, health, economy, and innovation.”
9. “This collaboration is open to any actor who can contribute to the objectives of this Green Deal.”

(Departement Omgeving, 2021)

Appendix 6: Reasons for signatories to participate in the GDPS, related to capacity building and knowledge gaining

The importance of the nine predefined reasons for signatories to participate in the GDPS was investigated (see questions in Appendix 1). Acquiring knowledge on the necessary steps to achieve a protein transition in Flanders (transformation knowledge) emerged as the most important reason for their organisation to participate in the GDPS. It was for all respondents one of the reasons to participate. The establishment and strengthening of professional connections were also deemed nearly as important.

Respondents rated the acquisition of knowledge about the values and norms of Flemish stakeholders concerning the protein transition almost as high as understanding the envisioned future of the Flemish protein transition, ranking these two concepts linked to target knowledge respectively fourth and third in terms of importance. It was for most respondents one of the reasons to participate.

Gaining knowledge about the problems associated with the current Flemish food environment was ranked fifth in importance, with slightly more than half of the respondents considering it important or somewhat important. Understanding the complexities associated with the protein transition followed closely on the sixth place.

Acquiring knowledge about the issues related to Flemish protein overconsumption ranked seventh, with slightly less than half of the respondents deeming it important or somewhat important. The issues surrounding Flemish animal protein consumption were considered of lesser importance. Finally, the least important reason to participate was the acquisition of skills for engaging in future collaborations.

Some signatories mentioned that their primary objectives for participation were to enhance mutual understanding between government and other stakeholders, foster connections between organisations that might not ordinarily interact, and gain insights into effective and appropriate communication strategies regarding the protein transition.

Appendix 7: Various additional activities to advance the protein transition beyond the GDPS

By GDPS signatories:

These included projects within the education sector, such as the School 2030 programme, which focuses on sustainability in schools, including food-related aspects. Some nonprofit signatories also made the 'Partijwijzer', among others indicating which political parties were open to binding objectives for production and consumption of plant-based food. Furthermore, some signatories participated in other initiatives like the Next Food Chain, a company network with producers of plant-based food and knowledge institutes. They aimed to share insights and collaborate with other stakeholders to drive change, such as through nudging strategies to encourage retailers to offer more plant-based options.

Some signatories also developed actions with partners who were not participating in the GDPS, like other cities, higher education institutes or nonprofit organisations (Departement Omgeving, 2022).

Several signatories also organised or participated in the Protein Festival ('Eiwitfestival'). Higher education institutions also incorporated the protein transition theme into thesis topics. Certain nonprofit signatories centred their entire operations around advancing the protein transition, including enabling the Vegan Supermarket Ranking, the V-label, and voluntary work. Additionally, some signatories were involved in broader related activities, such as agricultural production and projects at the Belgian level. Authorities from the Flemish Government also participated in working groups related to the Flemish Food or Protein Strategy, and the circular food chain agenda, ensuring attention towards the protein transition. A supplier of ingredients had set sales targets for plant-based proteins, and a food wholesaler establishes sales targets for plant-based products, which were not classified as GDPS activities.

By organisations outside the GDPS:

For instance, a song addressing the protein transition by the comedy show 'De Ideale Wereld', although not organised as part of the GDPS, could play a role in raising awareness. Additionally, Flemish talk shows occasionally discussed the protein transition, and the renowned TV chef Jeroen Meus had featured vegetarian dishes on his programme. Other initiatives included organisations introducing more plant-based options. The 'Week Zonder Vlees' campaign was also first launched in Belgium in 2023, inspired by the Dutch version.

DIVISION OF BIOECONOMICS
DEPARTMENT OF EARTH AND ENVIRONMENTAL SCIENCES
UNIVERSITY OF LEUVEN
GEO-INSTITUTE
CELESTIJNENLAAN 200 E – BOX 2411
3001 LEUVEN, BELGIUM

erik.mathijs@kuleuven.be
ees.kuleuven.be/bioecon